
Exploring the Association between Parental income, Child labour and Access to Basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district, Nigeria.

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Abstract:

The study investigates the associations between parental income, child labor and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district. Using quantitative data method, we analyze data from a structured questionnaire. A sample of 150 respondents was selected. Our findings indicate that parental income and child labor are significant predictors of access to basic education. Additionally, we find that access to basic education is limited in the district and that this is closely tied to poverty and child labour. We recommend targeted interventions to improve access to education including implementing programs to support families in poverty, building more schools as well as strengthening school-community collaboration.

Keywords: Parental income, Child Labour, Access, Basic Education

1. Introduction

Access to education is widely recognized as a fundamental tool for promoting socioeconomic development. In line with this recognition, the Education for All initiative has made provision for every child in the world to have full access to education. To ensure the attainment of this provision, many countries including Nigeria have introduced programs and measures to increase access to education among their citizens. The introduction of basic education in Nigeria in 1999 was a significant step towards achieving this goal. The main objective of basic education in Nigeria as stated by Blessing (2018) is to inculcate in all citizens a strong consciousness for education and a great commitment to its vigorous promotion, as well as provision of free, global basic education for all Nigerian children of school age.

Despite the importance of access to education, there are still challenges that hinder its attainment in many parts of Nigeria, including the Jigawa North senatorial district. One of the challenges that have been identified is child labour. Child labour is a serious issue that affects the ability of children to access basic education. In many cases, children are forced to work to support their families (Adegbanro, 2017), and which prevent them from attending school. Additionally, parental income plays a significant role in determining a child's access to basic education. Children from low income families are more likely to be engaged in child labour and have limited access to schooling.

The purpose of this study is to explore the association between parental income, child labour and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district. The findings of this study will contribute to the existing knowledge on the factors that influence access to basic education in Nigeria and provide insights in to the challenges faced by children in Jigawa North senatorial district and other parts of the state. The results of this study will inform the development of policies and interventions aimed at improving access to education in the region.

Research objectives

This study has the following objectives:

- i) To assess the relationship between parental income and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district, Nigeria.
- ii) To assess the relationship between child labor and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district, Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section deals with theoretical and empirical review on parental income, child labor and access to basic education.

2.1 Theoreticalreview

Thisstudy adopts both investment theory and poverty of opportunity theory explaining the relationship between parental income, child labor and access to basic education. Investment theory according to Iruka et al (2014) states that children parental income aid parents to invest in their children by supplying them with time, resources and money boosting materials, activities and schooling opportunities. This theory is related with the current study because the researchers assess the association between parental income and access to basic education.

Additionally, poverty of opportunity theory is used to analyze the effect of differential return on the incidence of child labor (Congdon, 2008). He further explained that parents determine the fate of their children by deciding on whether the child will work or go to school. The children at school acquire human capital, while those children not attending school resort to work. This theory is linked to our study because the current study intends to

determine whether child labor significantly impact on access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district.

2.2 Parental income and access to basic education

Parental income refers to any income receive in a month or a year by parents which may affect their children access to basic education. According to Mayer (2002) parental income is a vast concept which positively influenced all segments of child wellbeing. This is why socioeconomic status and parent's level of education are viewed as psychological and sociological parameters that affect children educational outcomes. It has been observed that children from low income families experience lower level of education quality (Harma & Spies, 2018), this makes parental income a very influential and critical factor of major social outcomes including educational achievement, level of consumption, asset holdings, home ownership and home value (Torche & Spileman, 2013). A study conducted by Kemanaeand Mojokoya (2022) found that low parental income is a stumbling block on access to education and hinders educational achievements. In a similar study, on family size, schooling and child labour, Harry (2020) discovered that children from low income home experience little resources while attending school and that parental income determines student's survival rates.

2.3. Child labor and access to basic education

Study conducted by Silbaway and Majialuwe (2024) on the effect of child labor on educational achievement in Tamale Ghana found that poverty, peer impact, cultural and social norms, gender roles and culture of fostering are the major causes of child labor and that child labor leads to poor educational outcomes. There is evidence that combining school and work leads to poor school attendance and absenteeism (Assad et al, 2017). Additionally, Soussi and Bouhilla (2017) argue that children engage in child labor are more likely to drop out of school with girls mostly as victims. Previous research have attributed the problem of child labor to poverty, joblessness, condition of family members, low aspiration. Parental debt, high cost of education, poor access to education and early marriage (Ahad, et al, 2021).

The aforementioned literature review stressed the influence of parental income, child labor and access to education. However, none of these studies combined parental income and child labor variables together in a single study and show how they influence access to basic education and hence the need for this study.

3. Methodology

This study is a quantitative one and hence adopts a cross-sectional survey approach to investigate the association between parental income, child labour and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district, Nigeria. The population for the study comprises all primary 6 pupils enrolled in the 12 local government areas of Jigawa North senatorial district, Nigeria. The total population of 7613 students was determined. The study employed a stratified random sampling technique to select representative sample from the population. The strata are 12 local government areas, and within each stratum, a random sample of students was selected proportionally based on the size of the local government area. Overall, the total sample size for this study is 150 which was ascertained using Krejcie and Morgan table for sample selection. For research instrument, a structured questionnaire was used and validity and reliability testing was done. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 The findings on the relationship between parental income and access to basic education

The first objective of the study is to assess the relationship between parental income and access to basic education. Table 1 summarizes the

Findings:

Table 1.

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Regular School Attendance	Yes	50	33%
	No	100	77%
Access to Nearby school	Yes	63	42%
	No	87	58%
Regular payment of school fees and other dues	Yes	55	36%
	No	55	64%
Access to books and learning Materials	Yes	52	35%
	No	98	65%
Access to School Uniform	Yes	49	33%
	No	100	67%

Based on the data provided in table 1, it is clear that only 33% of the pupils in the area of study attend school regularly, about 58% do not have access to a nearby school and 64% find it difficult to pay school fees and other dues. More so, 65% of the sample have no access to learning materials and 67% attest that they lack school uniform. From this finding, it is evident that a significant positive relationship exists between parental income and access to basic education in the study area. This finding agrees with that of Kemanae and Mojokoya (2022) who found that parental income is an obstacle to the realization of full access to education and academic achievement.

Objective 2 of the study tries to assess the relationship between child labour and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district. This is summarized in table two below:

Table 2: The findings on the relationship between child labour and Access to basic education

Objective 2 of the study tries to assess the relationship between child labour and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district

Statement	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Have to get food every day before going to school	Yes	93	62%
	No	54	36%
Participate in Domestic work every day before going to school	Yes	103	69%
	No	47	31%
I hawk goods every day in the Morning Before going to school	Yes	76	51%
	No	74	49%

The data in table 2 above shows that more than 60% of the pupils have to work to get money and food every day before going to school with 69% of the sample attesting that they engaged in domestic activity before going to school. More so, 51% of the pupils in the study area

participate in selling goods in the morning before they attend school. This agrees with Oni (2017) study that combining school and work leads to poor attendance and low educational achievement.

To sum it up, these findings have a lot of implications. It is concerning that such high percentage of the sample have to fend for themselves, sell goods and participate in some economic activity which affect their schooling.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the data provided, it is clear that there is a significant association between parental income, child labor and access to basic education in Jigawa North senatorial district. The findings indicate that a high percentage of the sample do not have access to learning materials and lack a nearby school and the bulk of the pupils have to work before going to school. These findings are alarming as they indicate that there are significant barriers to accessing basic education in the district. Overall, this research will contribute to the development of effective educational policies and interventions that address these critical issues.

5.2 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were given:

- i. Government should provide financial assistance and support to poor families as this will help in keeping their children in school.
- ii. Schools and communities need to work together to identify and address any underlying issues that may be contributing to child labor.
- iii. Community and government must join hands to establish more basic education schools in the district and equip them with relevant teaching and learning materials.
- iv. School buses should be made available in the district to transport pupils to school.

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